

Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel- and Copper(II) with 2-Furfurylidene-*p*-nitroaniline and 2-Furfurylidene-*m*-nitroaniline Schiff Bases

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Schiff base metal complexes have been a widely studied subject because of their industrial and biological applications^{1,2}. Structural studies and antimicrobial activities of the Schiff bases of furfuraldehyde with other amines have been reported^{2,3}.

The present investigation aims at the synthesis and antimicrobial studies of 2-furfurylidene-*p*-nitroaniline and 2-furfurylidene-*m*-nitroaniline Schiff bases and their metal chelates with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the metal complexes of furfurylidene-*p*-nitroaniline indicate metal-ligand stoichiometry for all the three complexes as 1 : 2. The conductivity data of the complexes in methanol (10⁻³ M) confirm the bi-bivalent electrolytic nature (186–206 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹). The magnetic moment values of all the complexes indicate the high-spin octahedral geometry⁴.

The ir ligand band at 1 630 cm⁻¹ shifted to lower side by 50 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, thereby suggesting participation of azomethine group in the coordination. The furan C–O–C moiety band (1 205 cm⁻¹) of the ligand appeared at 1 170 ± 20 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicating the involvement of furan oxygen in coordination. Water in the complexes may be present as lattice or coordinated. The bands for all the complexes appearing at 3 450 ± 10, 1 600 ± 20 and 10 ± 20 cm⁻¹ due to stretching, bending and rocking modes respectively, suggest coordinated mode of

water molecules⁵. The presence of new bands in the spectra of the complexes around 410 ± 20 and 510 ± 15 cm⁻¹ are assigned to M–N and M–O bonding respectively. The vibration of sulphate ion appears at 1105 ± 10 and 605 ± 10 cm⁻¹. This in association with conductance data indicate about the uncoordinated nature of sulphate group.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex show two bands at 16.00 and 20.00 kK corresponding to transitions ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g} (v₂) and ⁴T_{1g} (F) → ⁴T_{1g} (P) (v₃) respectively. The first band (v₁) (⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}) should theoretically occur at 7.10 kK and the values of 10Dq, B, β, v₃/v₂ and LFSE are 8896, 979, 0.87, 1.25 and 89.19 respectively, which are in fair agreement with the predicted value of octahedral complex. The Ni^{II} complex shows three bands at 10.50, 18.20 and 27.02 kK corresponding to (v₁) ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{2g} (F), (v₂) ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{1g} (F) and (v₃) ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{1g} (P) respectively. This confirms the octahedral geometry. The values of 10Dq, B, β, v₃/v₂ and LFSE 10500, 789, 0.75, 1.48, (-)249 and 150.82 respectively also support the same view. The calculated value of %β indicates a partial covalent character of this Ni–L bond. The Cu^{II} complex gives a single broad band at 13.00–14.50 kK (²E_g → ²T_{2g} transition). The electronic band position and LFSE value (101.19) are in good agreement with the octahedral geometry of the copper(II) complex⁶.

The analytical data of the furfurylidene-*m*-nitroaniline metal complexes show the metal-ligand stoichiometry as 1 : 2. The molar conductance values

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour, Decomp. temp. °C)	Analysis % Found / (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
	C	H	N	M	
C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃ (FPNA) (Yellow, 110–04)	61.10 (60.90)	3.70 3.00	12.90 12.20)	–	–
Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ .SO ₄ .H ₂ O (Sandstone, 236–40)	41.00 (40.10)	3.40 2.90	8.70 8.00	9.00 9.90)	4.91
Ni(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ .SO ₄ .2H ₂ O (Olivegreen, 204–10)	40.10 (40.80)	3.60 3.00	8.50 8.90	8.80 8.10)	3.10
Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ .SO ₄ .H ₂ O (Brown, 200–05)	40.90 (40.00)	3.40 2.90	8.60 8.10	9.70 9.00)	2.40
C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃ (FMNA) (Buff, 115–20)	61.10 (60.90)	3.70 3.00	12.90 12.30)	–	–
Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃).SO ₄ .H ₂ O (Brown, 195–200)	42.00 (41.00)	3.20 2.80	9.00 8.80	9.30 9.00)	4.52
Ni(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃) ₂ SO ₄ .2H ₂ O (Brown, 252–60)	43.70 (42.90)	3.30 2.60	9.20 8.90	9.60 8.30)	Diamag.
Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃) ₂ SO ₄ .2H ₂ O (Blackish, 232–40)	42.10 (41.00)	3.10 2.50	8.90 8.70	10.00 9.60)	1.91

of the complexes (in DMF) in the range 25–30 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ favour the nonelectrolytic nature of the complexes. The room temperature magnetic moments of complexes suggest tetrahedral structure for the cobalt complex and square-planar for the nickel and copper complexes⁹.

The ir ligand band at 1 620 cm^{-1} shifted to lower side in the complexes (1 580 \pm 20 cm^{-1}) suggesting participation of azomethine group in complexation. The furan C–O–C band (1 210 cm^{-1}) shifted slightly (\pm 5) in the complexes, thus ruling out its participation in coordination leaving ligand to act as monodentate species. Two bands observed at 3 450 \pm 10 and 1 610 \pm 10 cm^{-1} in the complex are due to stretching and bending modes of water. The third and fourth bands are untraceable. This suggests the presence of only lattice water. The new bands in the spectra of all the complexes appear at 425 \pm 10 (M–N) and 500 \pm 10 cm^{-1} (M–O). The bands at 1 040 \pm 10, 980 \pm 10 and 650 \pm 10 cm^{-1} may tentatively be assigned to coordinated bidentate sulphate moiety in the complexes⁵.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex show one band at 15.90 kK for $^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}$ (*P*) transition. However, on the basis of magnetic and spectral data, tetrahedral geometry for this complex is suggested. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complex

showed two bands at 17.20 and 26.70 kK (the first band is absent) which are assignable to transitions $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ respectively. These findings suggest square-planar geometry for this complex. The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complex shows two bands at 14.52 and 15.08 kK assignable to transitions $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$ and $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ respectively, which suggest square-planar geometry for the copper complex⁶.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the six compounds were evaluated for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria solani*, *Alternaria carneus* and *Colletotricum capsici* at a concentration of 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ employing the growth technique⁷ and percentage inhibition was calculated. All the metal chelates exhibited significant fungitoxicity (zone of inhibition 10–30 mm) when compared to griseofulvin (standard) (20–80 mm). The fungistatic activity of the metal chelates was found to be in the order : Cu > Ni > Co.

Experimental

M.p. was determined on a Toshniwal melting point apparatus. Electronic spectra (MeOH) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on an Acculab-10 spectrophotometer

at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibility in the solid state was measured at room temperature (306 K) by the Gouy's technique. Conductance was measured on an Elico conductivity bridge. The purity of compounds was monitored by tlc on silica plates.

Preparation of ligands : 2-Furfurylidene-*p*-nitroaniline and 2-furfurylidene-*m*-nitroaniline were synthesised by adding a methanolic solution of 2-furfuraldehyde (0.01 mol) to a methanolic solution of *p*-nitroaniline and *m*-nitroaniline (0.01 mol) in 1 : 1 ratio followed by reflux on a water-bath for about 5 and 6 h respectively. The ligands 2-furfurylidene-*p*-nitroaniline (yellow coloured) and 2-furfurylidene-*m*-nitroaniline (buff coloured) were obtained and were crystallised from methanol (m.p. 100° and 120° respectively).

Preparation of complexes : A methanolic solution of the appropriate metal salt $M(n)SO_4 \cdot nH_2O$ (0.01 mol) was added to a methanolic solution of the ligand 2-furfurylidene-*p*-nitroaniline or 2-furfurylidene-*m*-nitroaniline (0.02 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 4–9 h. The resulting coloured complexes were washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure over $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator followed by heating in an oven at 60°. The complexes were air-stable, nonhygroscopic and soluble in methanol, ethanol and dimethylformamide.

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References

1. E. SINN and C. N. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 391; S. YAMADA and A. TAKEUCHI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **43**, 187; M. N. HUGHES, "Inorganic Chemistry of Biological Processes", Wiley, New York, 1981.
2. A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 339.
3. N. S. BIRADAR and T. R. GOUDAR, *Curr. Sci.*, 1974, **43**, 740; V. G. KULKARNI, N. ASHTAPUTRA, N. N. SIRMADAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 111; C. L. JAIN and P. N. MUNDLEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 432.
4. R. L. DATTA and A. SYAMAL, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", 2nd. ed., Affiliated East-West, New Delhi, 1993.
5. C. P. DUBEY, H. DUGGAL, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 550; C. R. PANDA, V. CHAKRABORTY and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 914; A. C. HIREMATH, H. B. HALLI and N. V. HUGGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 72, 189; K. MUKKANTI, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 277; K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1986.
6. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", 2nd. ed., Wiley-Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1976, p. 52; G. WILKINSON, "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", Pergamon, New York, 1987, Vol. 2; A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
7. M. B. HOGALE, B. N. PAWAR and B. R. KHOT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 361; M. A. SAID, *Proc. Saudi Biol. Soc.*, 1984, **7**, 165.

